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Radiochemical and Thermal Studies of the Copper(II)-Exchanged Form of Synthetic Zeolite Linde Sieve A

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Synthetic zeolite Linde Sieve A displays a double ion-sieve action. Only small cations can penetrate the single 6-rings into the beta cages. Ion exchange equilibria in Zeolite A have involved mostly univalent and divalent counterions¹. The radiochemical and thermal studies of a few cation-exchanged forms of the zeolite have already been reported^{2,3}. The present study of copper(II)-exchanged form of 4A shows evidence of hydrated copper(II) ions in the zeolite structure.

Experimental

The bulk supply of the synthetic zeolite used for cation-exchange with copper(II) was from the Union Carbide International Company, U. S. A. and had a lot number 440522. The sample of the zeolite, obtained from the bulk, and its copper(II)-exchanged form were prepared by the method reported by earlier workers⁴. AnalaR quality of copper(II) chloride was used for cation exchange. The exchanged form of the zeolite was washed thoroughly to remove all free copper(II) ions. The washings were treated with ammonia solution for this purpose. The copper zeolite was irradiated for 5 minutes in a neutron flux of 1.3×10^{12} neutrons/cm²/sec. to get copper-64 by neutron, gamma reaction. The gamma spectrum of the radioactive sample confirmed the presence of copper-64. The copper-64 content was measured in the zeolite against the standard copper(II) chloride which was simultaneously irradiated under similar conditions. The detectors used were Nuclear Enterprise 8312 Automatic Beta Gamma Spectro-

Fig. 1: TGA of Copper zeolite

meter and Princeton Gamma-Tech. Ge(Li) Detector (Model LGC 4.5 SD) using data presentation units like model 291 for memory, model 292 for display and model 293 for control. The zeolite was found to contain about 40% copper which was far greater than that expected in a completely exchanged Cu_2A zeolite ($\text{A} = \text{Al}_{1.2}\text{Si}_{1.2}\text{O}_4^{2-}$). The copper zeolite was heated to 110° and 650° and these preheated samples were treated with a saturated solution of NH_4Cl aq. The radiochemical analyses of these samples showed about 33% and 10% exchange respectively with NH_4^+ ions.

The thermal studies of the copper zeolite were carried out on a Dupont 990 Series unit for DSC and TGA, under nitrogen and at a heating rate of $20^\circ/\text{minute}$. The curves are reproduced in Figs. 1 and 2.

The greater percentage of copper(II) ions in the zeolite can be reasonably explained as due to the presence of hydrated form of copper(II) in the zeolite. Concentrated solutions of copper(II) chloride contain $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ ions. Although Vansant⁵ reports only partial exchange of copper(II) ions in zeolites X and Y, complete exchange takes place in the case of zeolite 4A.

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Fig. 2: DSC of Copper zeolite

Discussion

Copper(II) zeolite displays a strong DSC endotherm at 68° and an even stronger endotherm at about 290° . Corresponding weight loss steps (15% between 0° and 290° and 14% between 290° and 650°) can be observed in the TGA curve which has an additional weight loss step around 590° . Loss of water is believed to take place atleast at the first two temperatures but decomposition, presumably of the adsorbed hydrated $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, starts beyond 590° . Results of NH_4^+ (I)-exchange show that the zeolite is partially stable at 650° .

References

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